

Interrogating the Balance between Broadcast Media and Indigenous Communication Systems in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This was carried out to interrogate the balance between radio/television and indigenous communication systems. Survey research method was used through a structured questionnaire which helped to elicit responses from respondents. The population size for the study was 421,300 which represented the projected population of Khana Local Government Area with a growth rate of 2.4%. Using the Krejcie and Morgan table (1970), a sample size of 384 was obtained which formed the sample size for the study. Finding showed that the indigenous communication systems were veritable tools in the dissemination of information in Khana Local Government Area which was the area of study for this research, as the advent of modern media of communication has not supplanted the traditional media of communication. The study concluded that both systems can co-exist and operate perfectly if blended together and recommended amongst others, that since the modern communication systems (radio / television) have the advantage of a wider coverage and reach, they should be integrated into the indigenous communications systems for efficient and effective communication arrangements.

Keywords: Indigenous, Communication, Traditional Systems, Broadcast

Introduction

Communication is as old as human. It is important both for an individual and also for the society. Communication means the sharing of ideas, message, concept and feeling to another using any form of medium. On the other hand, indigenous communication is the process of using locally oriented media to exchange and pass message to the community people such as folklore, drama, dance drama, gung, storytelling, drum, flute, festival, proverb, local tambourine, among others.

The term 'communication' has so many definitions, depending on one's intention and orientation. Asemah (2011) opines that communication implies sharing, interaction, dialogue and understanding. The key word in the above definition is sharing. Seema (2022) defines communication as the interchange of thoughts or ideas; the transmission

of information, consisting of discriminatory stimuli, from a source to recipient. Therefore, for life to have meaning, communication must play a pivotal role in all human engagements.

Societies overtime, have developed modes of communication which are peculiar to them, and which are also handed down from one generation to another. Such communication modes, with native embellishments, are collectively known as indigenous communication system. Upholding this view, Adebisi (2015) opines that indigenous communication is a system and process of communication in use before external cultural influence. It emanates from, exists with and is used by the people. It usually takes the form of rituals, town criers, folk theatre, folktales, signals, music, dances, religious practices, festivals and symbols (Asemah, 2011).

Before the evolution of modern communication (radio and television), societies exploited the traditional communication system in the dissemination of information and in the achievement of mutual cohesion within the indigenous sphere. These traditional communication systems are local in their nature. Hence, Umoren (2022) considers traditional communication as basically used to refer to indigenous communication media systems available in various communities in various cultural settings. In Bonny Local Government Area of Rivers State, most of these traditional communication media aforementioned amongst numerous others still hold sway.

There is no gain saying that the indigenous communication system has played significant roles in the dissemination of information within the local sphere. However, the craving for better and faster ways of communicating, gave birth to the modern communication media otherwise known as exogenous communication. As the name implies, modern communication media, are the new ways of communicating that are alien to the traditional people or society. According to Mundy & Compton as cited in Nkohla & Okyere-Manu (2018), modern communication is communication that is transferred via technology and media platforms such as television, radio and newspapers.

Ofer & Azzai (2011) give more insight on some of the forms of exogenous or modern communication as including verbal, visual, audio, texting, video, social networks, multimedia, online interaction, e-mail, virtual forums, archives, websites, digital libraries and-databases-. With the evolution of radio/television and other forms of modern media of communication, some scholars argue that the traditional media of communication may likely lose their worth or go into extinction (Nkohla & Okyere-Manu, 2018). However, others still contend that the modern communication media have not in any way supplanted the traditional forms of communication, which have been engrained in the African traditional system (Ndolo 2006, Wilson 1997, cited in Asemah 2011). Pepple (2015) posits further that the traditional system of communication is prevalent in the local communities as information of some issues are passed on the individuals by the traditional news man.

Giving the prevailing arguments, this paper therefore sets out to critically examine the concept of indigenous communication by interrogating the balance between broadcast media and the indigenous communication system, especially in communicating development programmes and sharing of indigenous information among the people of Khana Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Ascertain the impact of indigenous communication system in the dissemination of development information and sharing of indigenous knowledge among the people of Bonny Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. Investigate the extent to which broadcast media have been effective in the dissemination of information in Bonny Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. Ascertain the extent to which the advent of modern communication media have affected the use of indigenous communication system in Bonny Local Government Area of Rivers State.
4. Ascertain the level of feasibility of the integration of indigenous communication system in modern communication system.

Review of Related Literature

Every culture and tradition in Africa is marked by its unique way of communication. Indigenous communication includes the transmission of entertainment, news, persuasion, announcements, and social exchanges of every type using the traditional or local modes of communication. Upholding this view, Adebisi (2015; p1) posits that indigenous communication is “a system and process of communication in use before external cultural influences.” He contends that, it is local communication that is unique to a given culture and that which existed before the arrival of modern mass media which is a formally organised bureaucratic system of communication. Traditional communication system refers to the methods of communication that have been used for centuries, such as face-to-face conversations, letters and telegrams. Ndolo, cited in Asemah (2011) posits that:

“Every society’s growth, survival and continuity depends on among other things, a system of communication through which people could exchange ideas and feelings; an economic system, the production of goods and services, a health system to counteract diseases and ensure human reproduction, a socio-political system to maintain control and order and a defence system to protect their territories against external aggression.”

The above assertion points to the fact that the traditional communication system involves the various modes or channels of disseminating indigenous knowledge and information within the local sphere. Mundy & Compton (1995) as cited in Nkohla & Okyere-Manu (2018) posit that the indigenous communication systems have been around for quite some time and can be traced as early as before the presence of modern communication media platforms used in this age and time. These traditional modes of communication are still very much relevant in our contemporary society as the modern mass media have not been able to phase them out (Asemah, 2011). Ellah (2013), suggests that indigenous communication could be called “oral media” which include: mythology, oral literature, proverbs, masquerades, rite of passage and other rituals expressed through oracy, music, dance and drama, use of costume and material symbol which accompany people from womb to tomb and beyond.

Since traditional communication processes and elements vary from one society to another, a precise classification of the indigenous modes and channels of communication in Africa may be extremely difficult. Akpabio (2003) cited in Asemah (2011) categorises indigenous communication into ten classes: (i) Instrumental communication; (ii) Demonstrative communication; (iii) Iconographic communication; (iv) Extramundane communication; (v) Visual communication; (vi) Institutional communication; (vii) Venue-oriented communication; (viii) Myths and legends; (ix) Folk tales, proverbs and parables; and (x) Natural phenomenon.

Asemah (2011, p. 337) highlights some of the problems of indigenous media as including:

- a. Lack of standard technical vocabulary in the description, analysis and conceptualisation of the media, channels and processes of traditional communication.
- b. Absence of an appropriate language, which can be universally applied in the description to all similar or identical concepts.
- c. There is also the diversity in the traditional political system in African societies and the conflict between it and the adopted system, which usually requires the use of western media structures, policies and facilities.
- d. Scientific and technological problems also affect traditional communication. The present level of development of traditional media in Africa is limited because some of the hardwares are not easily preserved, even though they can be replicated.

Literally, to broadcast means to spread, to scatter, as in planting. As against indigenous communication, Pepple (2011) as cited in Pepple (2023) posits that broadcasting is the use of radio waves, i.e., electromagnetic waves for transmitting and receiving messages over a long distance in the mass communication sense. Pepple posits further, that the offering of broadcasting is distinct from that of the print and indigenous media. Other unique attributes of broadcasting include immediacy, perversiveness, flexibility, voraciousness and other others.

Of the mass media generally accessible to Africans, radio is the most widespread and accessible. Asemah (2011) posits that because of its special qualities, radio can be a major force in bringing about development. Supporting the above assertion, Seema (2022) sees the radio to have established its place very fast in the minds of listeners as heavy doses of infotainment including music, drama and talk shows supplemented with news made radio popular overnight. The media have roles to play in promoting cultures of the people across societies. Asemah (2011) maintains that cultural traits that could be transmitted on the broadcast media include songs, drama, and local music and can be strategically linked with other cultural practices such as marriage and naming ceremonies to support the promotion of people's cultures. Pepple (2015) adds further that radio permeates all ethnic boundaries and is very ubiquitous, which makes it a most preferred medium of communication amongst the local folks.

Unlike other forms of mass media, television has become one of the most powerful media of mass communication because of its combination of sound, visual and motion. It is a medium for broadcasting audio-visual messages. Seema (2022) posits that

the television with a modest beginning in the 1960s has grown into a massive network of mass information and mass entertainment in today's world. Over the years, television has played a significant role in shaping Nigerian culture and promoting indigenous languages since it was launched in Nigeria in the 1960's. It is also used to advance the cause of the indigenous people of Bonny Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Experts have advocated the integration of indigenous communication media in modern communication systems in communicating development issues in Africa societies. This is against the backdrop that modern media have, without doubt, brought about rapid changes and development in the life of man, and thus can be very effective in the dissemination of indigenous information. Thus, Mundy & Compton (1995) cited in Nkohla & Okyere-Manu (2018) recommend four approaches as possible ways of making the integration feasible: (a) Exogenous communication of exogenous information through radio, TV, books, etc.; (b) Indigenous communication of indigenous information through indigenous forms; (c) Indigenous communication of exogenous information through indigenous channels, and (d) Exogenous communication of indigenous knowledge through radio, TV and newspaper.

Integrating indigenous communication in exogenous communication is a welcome development. However, it cannot have a smooth sail without bringing to bare some ethical issues. Thus Umoren (2022), and Zimmer *et al* (1996) cited in Nkohla & Okyere-Manu (2018) articulate the following to be some of the ethical issues that may arise as a result of such blend:

- a. **Ownership of Radio/Television:** Those who may not have access to the television or radio for example, may be excluded or marginalised in information sharing and this phenomenon may increase the digital divide between “the haves” and “the have nots.”
- b. **Access to Electricity/Power Supply:** Television and radio depend on electricity, generator or solar battery to function, hence, those in the local communities who may not have access or who may not afford these technologies, may be marginalised from information sharing.
- c. **Geographical Distance and Access to Network:** Geographical structure imposed by distance may arise. Network issues in connecting to particular TV stations may arise owing to geographical problems.
- d. **Extra-Mundane Nature:** Indigenous communication media depend so much on the extra mundane which includes incantation, invocation, libation and animal sacrifice. The traditional institutions shroud this extra-mundane communication in secrecy. This contrasts sharply with the open and highly accessible nature of modern media.
- e. **Attachment to Tradition:** Unnecessary attachment to tradition may result to resistance to changes and innovations.

f. **Reliance of Indigenous Communication Media Systems on Opinion Leaders:** Messages that do not emanate from opinion leaders in the communities are received with a very high level of suspicion and are likely to be disregarded.

g. **Illiteracy:** Information not disseminated in the local language on radio or television may pose some difficulties in understanding by the unlearned except there are interpreters.

h. **Prescription Error:** Communication of values from older to younger generations through modern media platforms can have an influence on the transference of values. The language, used to communicate these values, observation, body language together with the importance of social capital, must be factored in this kind of communication.

i. **Loss of authentic presence:** Indigenous communication encourages more authentic communication, as it encourages being in the presence of “the other(s)” while in communication thereby encouraging dialogue whereas modern communication does not thrive on face to face communication.

Umoren (2022) carried out a study on “Issues in Modern and Indigenous Communication Media Systems Convergence for Community Development in Nigeria.” The overall objective of the study was to ascertain the possibility of integrating modern (online) media to complement indigenous communication media systems in community development in Nigeria. The work was anchored on three theories: the technological determinism, mediamorphosis and development media theories. The qualitative analytical method was used. Findings from the study showed that factors like attachment to culture, extramundane nature of indigenous communication, cost, etc., pose serious challenge in the integration of both systems of communication. The study however concluded that integration of both systems is possible in spite of the challenges and therefore recommended among other things that rural communities should be linked to the national power grid to solve the problem of power in the rural areas; that government should integrate town criers into the information dissemination framework. Similarly, this study interrogating indigenous communication and broadcast media, has potentially x-rayed the need to blend indigenous communication with the dictates of the broadcast media by bringing them together in an agreeable manner which will only be made possible through legislation by according indigenous communication a national recognition in the media-sphere.

Similarly, Adebisi (2015) conducted a study on “Communicating Indigenous Knowledge through Exogenous Channel: A Comparative Content Analysis of Adedokun’s *Under the Brown Rusted Roofs* and Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart*.” The objective of the study was to interrogate the possibility of communicating indigenous knowledge through exogenous communication. This study did a comparative appraisal of indigenous content in Adedokun’s *Under the Brown Rusted Roofs* and Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart*. Findings from the study revealed that the two books are rich in indigenous information/knowledge in varying degrees.

The study reaffirmed that exogenous media can be a veritable complementary tool for the preservation of local or indigenous knowledge, culture and language. The study thus recommended that books and other exogenous media should continuously be utilised in the preservation and documentation of indigenous culture and communication systems;’ that the relationship between reading culture and the effectiveness of books to preserve indigenous knowledge be investigated. The study reviewed above aligns itself with the present study in that, whereas the study took a delve into the content analysis of two books (*Under the Brown Roofs* and *Things Fall Apart*), to ascertain the possibility of sharing indigenous knowledge using exogenous media, the present study considered the modern communication system (radio and television) to find out their similarities and dissimilarities with the indigenous communication system and the possibility of striking a balance between both communication systems.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on cultural effects theory and the technological determinism theory.

Cultural Effects Theory

The cultural effects theory recognises that the society is profoundly influenced by the media. The Marxists see the cultural effect model as a powerful influence which supports capital values and norms. This theory as propounded by Vivian (2009) examines how the mass media (books inclusive) can be used to influence values in different cultures. Thus, this theory recognises that the media audience is made up of people from a variety of social backgrounds. In considering this, Vivian (2009, p. 412) identifies two different perspectives through which the mass media can communicate values. The first is historical transmission which is the communication of wisdom from past generation to the future generation. The second perspective is contemporary transmission which captures how values are transmitted among contemporary communities and societies. This manner of communication may lead to changes. Thus, this theory is relevant to this study as it pinpoints the relevance of the indigenous communication system in information sharing within the local setting, while also harping on the evolution of the modern media which has come to complement the traditional communication system using modern technologies like books.

Technological Determinism Theory

This theory was propounded by Marshal McLuhan in 1964. The basic premise of this theory is that the media are extensions of the human body. The theory holds that the media not only alter their environment but the message they convey. Marshal McLuhan posits that the media bring new perceptual habit while their technologies create new environments. The theory states that technology, especially, the media, decisively, shape how individuals think, feel and act and how societies organise themselves and operate. Very importantly, the theory states also that the medium determines the content of communication (Asemah, 2011).

Umoren (2022) submits that the electronic communication would break down barriers such as time and distance encountered with traditional mass media. This theory, therefore, adds credence to this study, especially as it pertains to the modern communication media, which Marshall McLuhan argues that “inventions in technology invariably cause cultural change”

Methodology

The study adopted the survey method while the questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The population of the study comprised the entire people of Bonny Local Government which, according to the 2024 projection by the National Population Census, was 621,300. The sample size for the study was 384 calculated using the Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sampling table. The table has set up sample sizes alongside equivalent populations with confidence level at 95% and sampling error at 5%. The stratified random sampling technique was used to get the number of respondents from the 12 wards (strata) that make up Bonny LGA.

To get the individual respondents from the respective wards, the simple random sampling technique was used, which involved the selection of respondents at random from the sample frame (Ihechu & Ukaegbu, 2022). Thus, a total of 384 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents from the wards that make up Bonny LGA but only 257 copies were returned. This represented 66.9% return rate. The demographic data were analysed after the presentation and analysis of the questionnaire using tables and simple percentage.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: The impact of Indigenous Communication Systems in the sharing of Development Information and Indigenous Knowledge among the People of Bonny LGA of Rivers State

Variables	Responses	Percentages
Indigenous communication systems were mostly used in transferring cultural values among the people	100	38.91
Indigenous communication systems were not mostly used in transferring cultural values among the people	20	7.78
Indigenous communication systems were very effective in sharing development information among the people	67	26.07
Indigenous communication systems were effective in fostering unity among the people	70	27.23
Total	257	100

From the result of the table above, it can be deduced that indigenous communication systems were mostly used in transferring cultural values among the people as can be seen in the responses of most of the respondents, while a few thinks otherwise The implication is that respondents believe in the effectiveness of the traditional communication system which according to them are effective in fostering unity among them.

Table 2: Extent to which Radio and Television as Modern Communication Media have been Effective in the Dissemination of Information in Bonny LGA of Rivers State

Variables	Responses	Percentages
Very large Extent	10	3.89
Large Extent	30	11.67
Low Extent	110	42.80
Very Low Extent	107	41.63
Total	257	100

From the data presented in table 2 above it was adduced that radio and television are not entirely effective in the dissemination of development information and sharing of indigenous knowledge within the local context following the response from majority of the respondents. The implication is that residents of Bonny local government area do not get their basic information need from radio and television.

Table 3: Extent to which the advent of Radio/Television as Modern Communication Media have affected the use of traditional communications system in Bonny LGA of Rivers State

Variables	Responses	Percentages
Very large Extent	20	7.78
Large Extent	15	5.83
Low Extent	110	42.80
Very Low Extent	112	43.57
Total	257	100

Result from the table 3 above show that respondents agreed that radio and television have not affected the use of traditional communication system in Bonny LGA. The implication is that the advent of radio and television as modern communication media, have not in any way displaced the indigenous systems of communication

Discussion of Findings

The findings showed that the indigenous or traditional communication systems have not lost their relevance as veritable tools in the sharing of development information and indigenous knowledge among the people of Bonny LGA of Rivers. They were indeed very impactful. This was confirmed by the respondents who aligned with the stance that the indigenous communication systems were mostly used in transferring cultural values and sharing of development information among the people, corresponding with responses as shown in table 1 at 92.21 %. This finding lends credence to results of earlier studies and literature in this direction that the indigenous communication media have continued to remain the most coveted amongst the indigenous people in spite of the advent of radio and television (Asemah, 2011; Umoren, 2022). As Mundy & Compton (1995) cited in

Nkohla & Okyere-Manu (2018) observe, “indigenous channels can trigger development as informal interactions play a crucial role in influencing people to innovate or change.”

The results as portrayed in table 2 suggested that radio and television though modern communication systems of information dissemination, are not entirely effective in the dissemination of development information and sharing of indigenous knowledge within the local context. This is reflected in the percentage of 84.43, implying that radio and television though modern technological devices were not considered so much as veritable tools in the dissemination of information among the people of Bonny Local Government Area. This finding upholds the earlier stance by Wefwafwa (2014) as reviewed under empirical studies that:

The rural folks regard modern communication systems as superficial and unable to address their deep seated cultural issues. They argue that the synthetic, glamorous and vivid yet skeletal value of TV and radio lack the naturalness that they seek in communication. To them, metaphors, village dances and folk songs deliver messages far more effectively. After all, African rural life is largely natural and knows no glamour. For this, modern communication systems alone cannot address the cultural issues.

Additionally, in table 3, which queried the extent to which the advent of radio/television as modern communication media have affected the use of traditional communication system in Bonny LGA of Rivers State, it was adduced that the advent of radio and television as modern communication media, have not in any way displaced the indigenous systems of communication. However, they have continued to play complimentary roles to the indigenous modes of communication. This findings in this direction is in line with earlier literature and findings by scholars who opine that the indigenous modes of communication are still very much relevant in our contemporary society as the modern mass media have not been able to phase them out. The fact remains as Asemah (2011, p.331) aptly puts it, “they supplement the old ones or replace some of their functions, but not all their functions in their entirety. This findings also align with the view of Osho (2010, p. 187) as cited in Adebisi (2015) that “the contemporary Africa has continued to witness the simultaneous use of indigenous and exogenous media”.

Conclusion

The indigenous and modern communication systems have combined to shape the nature of communication the world over. It is true that the competition between the indigenous media and the modern media, is expected but such competition can be properly harnessed into achieving good communication experiences in all communication engagements. This can only be achieved through an integration of the indigenous communication system in modern communication system to achieve a harmonious communication encounter as prescribed by scholars and also collaborated by the present study, that the integration of both communications are possible. Such synergy will go a long way in helping to reposition the modes of information dissemination among the people of Bonny Local Government Area of Rivers State, which may have hitherto, frustrated development

efforts in the area. Against the backdrop of the findings of this study, it is recommended that since modern communication systems (radio and television) have the advantage of wider coverage and reach, they should be integrated in indigenous communication systems for efficient and effective communication engagements. Additionally, all factors that constrain the integration of indigenous communication system in modern communication system, should be addressed both by the government at the centre and the local authorities, to ensure harmony is achieved between the two communication systems. This will encourage the continuous thriving of the cause of communication in all fronts.

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